

Women, Peacebuilding, and Conflict Resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined women, peacebuilding and conflict resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. utilized the liberal feminist theory as a theoretical framework while relying on a survey design as its underlying research strategy. Data collected were analyzed through the use of t-test and the findings thereof reveal that there is a positive correlation between women participation peace building and conflict resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The study also showed that a good proportion of respondents agreed with the notion that women participation is imperative for effective involvement of women in peacebuilding and conflict resolution. Therefore, the study recommended that there is need to promote and encourage a substantial participation of women in all stages of peace building and conflict resolution talks based on the UN Security Council Resolution 1325 on women and armed conflicts. There should also be consistent awareness and sensitization campaigns targeted at reducing negative cultural norms and stereotypes that hinder women participation in peacebuilding and conflict resolution. Religious and community leaders should be engaged to promote gender equality and women's rights. More so, mechanisms should be established to monitor and evaluate the impact of peacebuilding and conflict resolution programmes aimed at enhancing women's involvement in peacebuilding and conflict resolution.

Keywords: *Women, Peace, Peacebuilding, Conflict. Conflict Resolution.*

Introduction

Conflicts have been described as inevitable and as a matter of fact regarded as normal in any human relationship. However, the management of these conflicts is where all the difference lies; conflict could actually be a channel through which positive change can be achieved or existing relationships marred. It could be violent or nonviolent, constructive or destructive, functional or dysfunctional. Conflict can also be positive, constructive and functional if only the right attitude is constructed towards it whenever it breaks out in the society. Unfortunately looking back at the history of Nigeria since the civil war, conflicts have consistently been violent with devastating effects on the Nigerian economy as well as its people, particularly women and children. The Boko haram insurgency, ethnic-religious clashes, and violent conflicts between nomadic pastoralists and some farming communities have in the past two decades brought untold hardship and sorrow: physically, emotionally and mentally to many Nigerian women (Gambo, 2015). Nigeria is one of the countries in the world that has experienced lots of violent conflicts and is still experiencing them, these conflicts come with devastating effects leading to massive loss of lives, destruction of properties, destruction of strategic infrastructures (Iloh, Ekeocha, & Ugwu, 2018). The prevalence of

this menace has necessitated the adoption of different methods to address the issue in the form of peacekeeping missions, panels of enquiry, and truth and reconciliation commissions. These peace processes have overtime mainly been dominated by men with little or no participation from women arising from gender inequality, patriarchal cultural practices that permeate into peacebuilding and conflict resolution (Nwandinobi, 2017; Raimi, 2020).

Conflict resolution and peacebuilding are important notions of global interest. Nigeria is constantly threatened by fanatical terrorists, suicide bombings, kidnapping, insurgency, and other violent acts, claiming the lives of innocent people. In Nigeria, so far, formal peacebuilding and conflict resolution efforts have not been extensively considered from a gendered point of view. For instance, Albert (1999) notes that men are the traditional channels of peacebuilding and conflict resolution since they were the heads of the different units at the urban, village, neighborhood, or household level. Consequently, previous efforts at conflict resolution and peacebuilding have mostly been the purview of men, and this male bias continues to prevail, especially about policy and key decision-making processes (Olaitan, 2018; Nwandinobi, 2017). The inclusion of communities and civil society, such as representatives of churches, mosques, and ethnic organizations, as members in peace talks, only serves to perpetuate male bias, as these are also mainly men. This is inevitable since women rarely occupy leadership roles, particularly religious ones. Potter (2008) postulates that the inclusion of women in conflict resolution and peacebuilding was superficial, questioning whether it is a “necessity” or a mere “nicety”. This notion begs the question of whether any value would be added by including women in conflict resolution and peacebuilding. These views explain, to some extent, why peacebuilding processes tend to be gender blind. However, this anomaly needs to be corrected if a strong, balanced, and sustainable peace is to be achieved. Conflict affects both men and women, albeit differently; therefore, all stakeholders must be included in striving for peace. Furthermore, excluding women in peacebuilding and conflict resolution processes is a serious lapse in judgment, because their inclusion could help reduce conflict and advance stability (Council on Foreign Relations [CFR], 2019). The United Nations Security Council Resolution (UNSCR) 1325 (2019) and resolution 2122 (2019) documents recommend the inclusion, representation, and participation of women in the peacebuilding and conflict resolution process. Some countries, including Nigeria, have National Action Plans (NAPs) in place to ensure that the peacebuilding and conflict resolution process is gender-sensitive. Indeed, Nigeria’s implementation of UNSCR still faces serious challenges despite a second launch of another National Action Plan for its execution (Binda, Rodriguez, Powley, Jarhum, & Gorani, 2018).

To some extent, women are now being included in formal peacebuilding and conflict resolution processes, but their participation is still less than adequate. Research indicates that between 1992 and 2018, only 3 percent of mediators were women, 4 percent signatories, and 13 percent negotiators in major peacebuilding processes. Furthermore, only two women have served, so far, as chief negotiators (UNSCR, 2019; CFR, 2019). Since women (and children) are especially vulnerable in conflict situations and suffer cruelty and displacement at the hands of combatants, it justifies the need for women to be involved in working toward peacebuilding and conflict resolution. Indeed, it is strongly

argued that wherever there is conflict, women should be part of the solution. The complex nature of peacebuilding and conflict resolution necessitates exploring all possible solutions, including the potential role of women in these processes.

Peacebuilding and conflict resolution are an important part of the development process, and essential to the security and stability of a nation. Women may help to bring fresh insights to peacebuilding and conflict resolution, based on their particular experiences, which may lead to achieving a more encompassing and sustainable peace. It is essential to adequately take into consideration the subtle and yet persuasive roles that women can play as wives, lovers, and mothers in lobbying for peace. Some authors are even of the view that women's contributions could not only improve the quality of the peace agreements reached, but also facilitate the implementation of the agreements since they have primary "responsibility for maintenance of the family and community, rebuilding peace and are the bearers of cultural and ethnic identity" (Insight on Conflict, 2017, p:361).

Globally, the United Nations has developed strategies through various institutions, protocols, and resolutions to prevent and manage conflicts. On the African continent, the African Union (AU) and the Economic Community of West Africa States (ECOWAS) have done the same in the West African sub-region. Despite these various structures, policies, and activities, conflicts have continued. However, the challenges of managing these various conflicts seem overwhelming on the current security architecture and personnel (Issifu, 2015). Discussions on the component or who is more suitable or more committed to the resolution of the conflict have emerged. In this regard, women have been perceived to be a critical part of peacebuilding and conflict resolution. Some have argued that the formal inclusion of women in the mechanism of peacebuilding and conflict resolution may be a panacea for the effective management of conflict. This, however, is not to say women are not also conflict instigators and combatants, as some took up arms, while others perpetrated violence against women and men alike. In all of these contestations, women have played and continue to play prominent roles in ensuring that the peace project is sustained.

There are so many debates as to the role women can play in the peacebuilding and conflict resolution process. However, their positive impacts have been indelible and far-reaching in many peacebuilding and peace negotiation exercises. Despite their result-oriented engagement in enacting peace, they are in some cases yet to be understood by some persons owing to the build-up perception and societal power relations. The numerical strength of women being approximately half of the population in most nations is a critical factor that should offer them a vantage position in peacebuilding and peace agreements, but they are limited. Women have to be considered not as a minority but as a significant group in itself, a group that embodies experiences and ideas of many others (Kazam, 2000). The absence of women implies the absence of justice, equality, and inclusion principles and therefore a partial approach to peacebuilding. Not always will women have specific demands different from the demands of

other social groups. Nevertheless, they can contribute to improving methodologies and communication among the parties and can help build trust among them. Based on this, the study examined women, peacebuilding, and conflict resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. This is the gap the study intends to bridge.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in this study;

- i. There is no significant relationship between women's participation and peacebuilding in the Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria
- ii. There is no significant relationship between United Nations Charter and conflict resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria
- iii. There is no significant relationship between deficiency in lobbying techniques and peacebuilding in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria
- iv. There is no significant relationship between advocacy and conflict resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Literature Review

Conceptual Clarification

We begin this section with a clarification of the key concepts, which are peace-building and conflict resolution. The term peacebuilding has gained recognition both within the academic and political arenas. Since it was initiated in 1992 by the then United Nations Secretary-General, Boutros Boutros-Ghali in a report titled – An Agenda for Peace, the UN made it an integral part of its mission and traditional mechanism for preventive diplomacy, peacemaking, and peacekeeping across the globe. However, despite the global acceptance and use of the concept, coining an actual definition remains untenable. This is because different sorts of actors- international coalitions, government agencies, and non-governmental organizations embrace the notion by making distinct contributions to its conceptualization, operationalization, and discourse, resulting in significant differences in its elucidation. Baylis and Smith (2001) define peacebuilding as “a peaceful, diplomatic activity, aimed at producing a settlement of the conflict and is normally carried out at the state-to-state level” or micro level. The interpretation of this definition involves methods described in Article 33 of the United Nations Charter, i.e., negotiation, enquiry, good offices, mediation, conciliation, arbitration, judicial judgment, resort to regional agencies, or agreements, or other peaceful means, but applied after a dispute has crossed the threshold into an armed conflict.

On the other hand, the term conflict resolution, which can also be referred to as dispute resolution, where arbitration and litigation processes are significantly involved, can be seen as encompassing the use of nonviolent resistance

measures by parties involved in an attempt to attain effective resolution. Conflict Resolution is conceptualized as measures and processes involved in facilitating the peaceful ending of conflict and retribution. Conflict resolution, according to John (2020), connotes containment of conflict through steps introduced to promote conditions in which collaborative and valued relationships control the behavior of conflicting parties; in other words, it ensures conflict prevention. According to Best (2012), conflict resolution is a process of reducing the negative and destructive capacity of conflict through several measures and by working with and through the parties involved in that conflict. It is a process that seeks to remove cognitive barriers to agreement and group synergy. It often covers an array of measures of conflict resolution: problem solving, super-ordinate goals, expansion of resources, avoidance, smoothing, compromise, authoritative command, and altering the human and structural variables (Osisioma, 2014).

State of Women's Participation in Peace Building and Conflict Resolution

It is a fact clear that peace building and conflict resolution are post- conflict initiative that tries to bring back to a very large extent, some form of normalcy and peaceful co-existence which can be sustained in conflict- torn areas over a very long period thereby avoiding the reoccurrence of violence, after violent conflict has reduced or has come to an end. This is usually achieved through intervention by the military, negotiations, etc. It will also suffice to add that while some of these definitions look at the process of peace building emerging only during the post-conflict situations, other definitions also include that peace building initiatives exist even during the pre-conflict period for the avoidance of violent conflict erupting in the first place. Because this process involves a series of transformative efforts, ranging from economic empowerment, political inclusion/participation, and social and psychological transformation, which usually takes a long time to achieve, commitment from all parties involved should be evident. For peace building to be effective in Nigeria, transforming the lives of women, whether victims or not, as well as building their capacity to contribute to peace, must be the focus. This is because when women are included in the peace processes at any level, without having the capacity to participate meaningfully, their inclusion will be limited and remain insignificant.

In the most general term, capacity consists of a party's ability to solve its problems and achieve its objectives. Capacity building aims to strengthen parties' ability to work together for their mutual benefit by providing them with the skills and tools they need to define problems and issues and formulate solutions (Maiese, 2005). Women in Peacebuilding is a concept that has found popularity within the Nigerian environment only recently. In a country like Nigeria, where patriarchy is entrenched, a change of attitude towards women's empowerment and inclusion in these peace-building processes is fundamental. At different levels of the processes, men and women should be seen to participate equally in the processes. This is because men and women are affected differently by conflict, and thus their definition of protection will also differ. Therefore, considering women's perspectives in peacebuilding is vital and provides a more holistic approach towards achieving peace. Quite a number of reasons abound as to why the capacity of Nigerian women should be enhanced towards their full participation in peacebuilding. First, more than

any group, women and children are the most affected; hence, their experience becomes valuable in building peace. Secondly, according to the 2006 census in Nigeria, women constitute almost half of the total population. The country's total population of 140,431,790 (2006) comprises 71,345,488 males and 69,086,302 females (total-facts-about-nigeria.com/population-of-nigeria.html), hence they form a significant percent even as victims (Iloh, Ekeocha, & Ugwu, 2018). Thirdly, women have been excluded from opportunities that will enhance their inclusion in formal peace processes, such as education, politics, policy making, governance, etc. Finally, that woman has been able to show through informal means their ability to promote peace, which only shows great potential waiting to be harnessed; hence, developing these potentials increases their ability to deliver meaningfully. "Capacity building goes well beyond the provision of basic needs. It is a matter of development at all levels of society and includes institutional development, community development, and economic development" (Maiese, 2005). Capacity building, according to the United Nations Development Programme, is the ability to perform functions, solve problems, and achieve objectives at three levels: individual, institutional, and societal.

The UNDP also added that capacity building 'is much more than training and includes the following: human resource development, the process of equipping individuals with the understanding, skills, and access to information, knowledge, and training that enables them to perform effectively' (gdrc.org/uem/capacity-define.html). This does not reflect the position of most Nigerian women in terms of their ability to participate in formal peace-building processes, especially those in the conflict-torn Northern Region. Hence, there is an obvious need for their capacity development since they form an important part of not just grassroots actors in peace building, but also potential actors on peace tables. If 'development' in this definition will mean an increase in their capacity to make their inclusion in the peace processes a meaningful one, then that is the way to go. Both peace building and capacity building are deliberate attempts towards leading a safer, better, and more productive life towards building peace. Joan B. Kroc outlined several strategic peace-building principles; one of them is that 'peace-building requires capacity and relationship-building at multiple levels' (Alliance for Peacebuilding, 2013). Therefore, conscious and consistent efforts must be made to realize these goals.

In Nigeria, women and girls are represented in every family either as grandmothers, mothers, wives, daughters, sisters, daughters-in-law, mothers-in-law, Aunts, sisters- in-law, nieces, or even maids. The culture in Nigeria is such that most families are made up of more than just the immediate family members; other members of the extended families also live with them for one reason or another. Unfortunately, this special group of people does not enjoy the same privileges that their male counterparts enjoy. The patriarchal culture in the Nigerian society and indeed Africa is largely responsible for this, which hitherto forms the foundation for their exclusion in all formal peace processes. This discrimination manifests itself across all facets of life; education, politics, decision-making processes, other formal sectors, businesses, etc. Hence, women with great potential have been forced to take the back seat and remain silent. As globalization and exchange of ideas and culture take place between Nigeria and the

developed world, it is expected that this obsolete patriarchal culture is thrown out of the window by now; unfortunately, that is not the case. Very few women are seen in the realms of affairs in the country, and this is reflected in various sectors, especially the public sector. Because women are grossly marginalized, they are in turn not adequately represented even on the peace table, where their definition of protection should be heard in order to achieve a more sustainable approach towards building lasting peace, being that they constitute a significant portion of the population and are the most affected during conflict.

Exposing the conflict resolution potential of women, Mutunga says, 'It is becoming increasingly accepted that women have unique opportunities for conflict resolution due to the unique role they play in society' (Mutunga, 2012, p. 369). Women are also uniquely and adversely affected by violent conflict because of their gender both during the conflict and after. It is in line with this realization that the United Nations, through its most important organ, the United Nations Security Council, adopted the UNSCR 1325 in 2000, a 'Landmark resolution on Women, Peace and Security' (un.org). As a member of the UN and a country that has had to contend with violent conflict, especially in the last two decades, the Nigerian government committed itself to the inclusion of women in the resolution of conflict and peace building. This was demonstrated to the world when it domesticated the resolution by launching the National Action Plan of the UNSCR 1325 in 2013 (Bell, 2013). This move for the domestication of the UNSCR1325 is very crucial, commendable, and a long-awaited one because Nigeria, just like any other Sub-Saharan country, is mainly patriarchal; thus, Women have been marginalized across various divides, and their voices are rarely heard or represented at the peace tables. However, since the domestication of this resolution in 2013, little progress has been made in terms of the full inclusion of women in this respect. The little progress, however, is not evident.

Indeed, ever since the upsurge of violent conflicts in Nigeria, the participation of Nigerian women in peace building represents a very marginalized and unbalanced one, one that shows women taking the initiative for peace building only within the non-formal sphere at the grassroots or community level. This is through avenues such as civic society groups, informal-female-based groups, etc., because that happens to be the only medium available for them, and very little or no representation in the governmental sphere. Speake (2013) further buttressed this point when he cited Diaz (2010, p.1) 'However, formal peace building and conflict resolution initiatives continue to ignore or marginalize issues of gender, and women's involvement in formal missions and talks remain low. This is a situation seen in Nigeria - only a few are included since very few can participate extensively.

Politics and policy are other areas where the marginalization of women is very glaring in Nigeria. Throughout the history of democracy in Nigeria, the story of women's participation in politics has been very low. At different times, the level of inclusion might differ slightly, but one common thing remains that women continue to be grossly marginalized in Nigerian politics and governance. According to a study by Zahrah Nesbitt-Ahmed, 'Of the 7160

candidates that contested in the April 2007 elections, only 628 were women, 25 candidates vied for the office of president, and only 1 was a woman, while five women contested for the office of vice president. Also, only 9 of the 109 senators are women (Nesbitt-Ahmed, 2011). Also, in the 2015 presidential elections in Nigeria, only one woman, Prof Oluremi Sonaiya of the Kowa party, contested and lost the election to the APC presidential candidate, Gen. Muhammadu Buhari. Records extrapolated from the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) showed that of all the 109 senators elected in the 2015 elections, only 7 were women (inecnigeria.org), and out of the 36 ministers in the present administration of President Muhammadu Buhari, only 6 are women. This pattern at the national level reflects clearly what is happening at the state and local levels too.

When women are not adequately represented in the political space, especially as legislators, it becomes challenging to enact gender sensitive laws that will liberate women to live their full potential. 'When women are discriminated against in the political arena, their experiences, talents and perspectives are shut out of the policy decisions of our democracies, and prospects for a better world are short-changed' (Bell, 2013). Unfortunately, this discrimination was further entrenched by the recent non-passing of the gender and equal opportunity bill by the legislators in the Nigerian senate. This is not surprising, seeing that out of 109 senators, only 7 are women. How can only seven voices speak effectively and vote successfully for gender sensitive bills on behalf of millions of other women in Nigeria? The more women are represented, the easier it is to have their voices heard and influence the enactment of laws and policy decisions that will benefit Nigerian women and young girls.

Theoretical Framework

The study utilizes the liberal feminist theory to explain the role of women, peacebuilding, and conflict resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The Utopian Socialist and French philosopher Charles Fourier is credited with having originated the word "feminism" in 1837 (Goldstein, 1982). The words "feminism" and "feminist" are purported to have first appeared in France and the Netherlands in 1872, Great Britain in the 1890s, and the United States in 1910. Liberal feminists are seeking to end women's exclusion from or underrepresentation in office, power, and employment; they seek women's equal rights in the military, including in combat. They see women's Protection as a way of keeping them from power and their dependence on men as compromising their claims to full citizenship, which is usually understood to include fighting for one's country. Other feminists are critical of Liberal feminists for seeking equality in masculinist institutions on men's terms. In different ways, they seek to change the institutions themselves to be women-friendly (Potter, 2008).

On a general note, liberal feminism is premised on the idea that gender inequality in society is a product of patriarchal and sexist patterning of the division of labor (Messer, 2002). Based on the assumptions of liberal feminism, gender is socially constructed. It is manifest in the division of labor, where domestic work that is devalued and not remunerated is assigned to women. In contrast, work outside the home is highly remunerated and is assigned to men. This whole phenomenon is perpetuated through patriarchal ideology (Messer, 2002). The theory explains

the lack of recognition for the role of women's organizations in peacebuilding and conflict resolution to our cultural beliefs and attitudes.

Despite associated criticisms, the theory is relevant in explaining the role of women in peacebuilding and conflict resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria because from the assumption of the theory it is believed that it is the men who are supposed to be involved in outdoor activities such as peacebuilding and conflict resolution while women are supposed to be involved in menial jobs such as childcare and housekeeping. Consequently, even though women have played important roles in peacebuilding and conflict resolution, their roles have not been recognized simply because they are women. Perhaps if these organizations were formed by women, their roles would have been acknowledged. This work therefore states that, for the women organizations to be deeply involved in peacebuilding and conflict resolution and their contributions to be appreciated, there has to be a change in our cultural beliefs and attitudes.

Methodology

The study was conducted in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The study utilized the survey research design due to its ability to aid data collection from a large population easily. Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria has fourteen (14) electoral wards. However, the study was restricted to five (5) selected electoral wards to include Udenin gida, Udenin, Odu, Akum, and Kana/Onda/Apawu electoral wards. The population of the group of people from the designated electoral wards stood at 123,338 (National Population Commission, 2024). The Cochran (1977) formula was used to determine the sample size of 384 respondents for the study. The sampling technique that was adopted for the study is a systematic random sampling. The technique allows for representativeness, efficiency and reduces bias. The study generated data via questionnaire and analysis was done using bivariate method through the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS v28).

Data Analysis

Table 1: *T-test Analysis of the Relationship Between Women Participation and Peacebuilding in Nasarawa*

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cat	t-crit
Male	112	2.12	0.16			
Female	245	2.79	0.19	3.83	8.13	1.69

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The t-test analysis of the difference in mean ratings of the relationship between women participation and peacebuilding in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria shows that the calculated t-value of 8.13 is above the t-critical of 1.96, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant

relationship women participation and peacebuilding in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Table 2: T-Test Analysis of the Difference in the Mean Responses of the Relationship Between United Nations Charter and Conflict Resolution

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cat	t-crit
Male	245	2.82	0.18			
Female	112	2.13	0.19	3.83	6.42	1.96

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The summary of the t-test analysis on difference in the mean responses of the relationship between United Nations Charter and conflict resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria showed that the calculated t-value of 6.42 is above the t-critical of 1.96, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that there is significant relationship between United Nations and conflict resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Table 3: T-Test Analysis of the Difference in the Mean Rating of Responses on the Relationship Between Deficiency in Lobbying Techniques and Peacebuilding

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cat	t-crit
Male	112	2.90	0.09			
Female	245	2.69	0.14	3.83	2.73	1.96

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The summary of the t-test analysis on the difference in the mean ratings of respondents with regard to the relationship between deficiency in lobbying techniques and peacebuilding in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria showed that the calculated t-value of 2.73 is above the t-critical value of 1.96. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, implying that there is a significant relationship between deficiency in lobbying techniques and peacebuilding in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Table 4: T-test Analysis of the Relationship Between Advocacy and Conflict Resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cat	t-crit
Male	112	2.12	0.16			
Female	245	2.79	0.19	3.83	8.13	1.69

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The t-test analysis of the difference in mean ratings of the relationship between advocacy and conflict resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria shows that the calculated t-value of 8.13 is above the t-critical of 1.96; therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that there is a significant relationship between advocacy and conflict resolution in the Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The examination of the results showed that there is a positive correlation between women's participation and peacebuilding, the United Nations Charter and conflict resolution, deficiency in lobbying techniques and peacebuilding, and advocacy and conflict resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The study also showed that a good proportion of respondents agreed that women's participation is imperative for effective involvement of women in peacebuilding and conflict resolution. It also revealed that economic empowerment will promote greater involvement of women in peacebuilding efforts.

The study further revealed that women's vocational skills acquisition programs will aid greater involvement of women in peacebuilding and conflict resolution. It also showed that grants and micro credit schemes will help ease women's economic marginalization and enhance women's involvement in peacebuilding. Also shown in the result was the relationship between Women's awareness of the United Nations Charter and women's active involvement in peacebuilding in the study area. Meanwhile, the results revealed that many respondents agreed that Civil society engagement plays an important role in awareness of the United Nations Charter, and hence women's participation in peacebuilding. This finding corroborates that of Schirch (2004), who found that a fundamental opportunity for building women's capacity for peace building is through prioritizing women's participation and training in vocational skills.

This discrimination against women and girls should be seen as obsolete, inappropriate, and dangerous for Nigeria at a time like this, hence should be proscribed. In order for Nigeria to move forward in this regard, free and compulsory education should be provided for young girls and women in Nigeria (North) by the government. Scholarships should be awarded for young school girls across various educational levels (especially at the secondary and tertiary levels) who are outstanding, to encourage them to develop their potential and that of the country at large. When women and girls are educated, their level of reasoning is greatly improved, and they can contribute meaningfully in society at different levels, whether in the family, community, or the boardrooms. Their potentials are harnessed. They can make informed decisions about themselves, their future, and even at the peace table. Education and training in vocational skills allow them to earn good jobs, and even become employers of labor, so they can liberate themselves from poverty and overdependence on their husbands and fathers. As widows, they are better able to fend for themselves and other members of their families.

Conclusion

The study examined women, peacebuilding, and conflict resolution in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. The study established that women play a significant role in peacebuilding and conflict resolution in the Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria. They served as mediators and negotiators. The study further affirmed that women's participation in peacebuilding and conflict resolution increases the chance of an agreement being reached in many situations.

Recommendations

Based on the findings drawn from the study, the following recommendations have been made to improve peacebuilding and conflict resolution in the Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

- i. Promote and encourage a substantive participation of women in all stages of peace building and conflict resolution talks based on the UN Security Council Resolution 1325 on women and armed conflicts.
- ii. The education and skill training of women and girls in Nasarawa Local Government Area of Nasarawa State, Nigeria, should be encouraged by both formal and informal stakeholders in education. This will enable them to gain valuable knowledge and skills for participation in peacebuilding and conflict resolution efforts.
- iii. There should be consistent awareness and sensitization campaigns to negative cultural norms and stereotypes that hinder women's participation in peacebuilding and conflict resolution. Religious and community leaders should be engaged to promote gender equality and women's rights.
- iv. Mechanisms should be established to monitor and evaluate the impact of peacebuilding and conflict resolution programmes and interventions aimed at enhancing women's involvement in peacebuilding and conflict resolution—regular assessment of these programmes to ensure that efforts are effective and can be adjusted as needed.

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